

FINITE ELEMENT POSTPROCESS METHOD FOR COMPOSITE PLATES WITH GENERAL LAYUPS

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SUMMARY: A postprocess method is developed for general layup configurations in the finite element framework. The previous developed postprocess method for symmetric cross-ply layup is extended for 2-dimensional various layup configurations. For the general layup configurations, not only shear angles but also reference in-plane displacement matchings are needed between higher order theory and first order shear deformation theory. Additionally, in-plane equilibrium equations of higher order shear deformation theory are utilized in each elements to satisfy the transverse shear free conditions at the top and bottom surface of the laminates. Basic framework of the postprocess method is preserved. In order to recover accurate transverse shear stresses, third order derivatives of w need to be calculated in each elements. Finite different schemes are used to compute reliable third order derivatives of the deflections. Numerical examples demonstrate the accuracy and simplicity of the present method for various layup configurations

KEYWORDS: postprocess method, first order shear deformation theory, efficient higher order plate theory, laminated composite plate, shear correction factors, energy equivalence, finite element method

I. INTRODUCTION

In the analysis of laminated composites, a first order shear deformation theory is adequate to predict the global behaviors. However, for the stress analysis of the detailed through-the-thickness behavior, refined models are required. Among the simplified higher order theories[1-4], an efficient higher order plate theory was developed by Cho and Parmerter [4,5] which satisfies through-the-thickness kinematics and statics. This higher order theory can provide accurate predictions for stresses and deformations. However, it requires C1 shape functions in finite element implementation[6] and its computations of the element stiffness matrix routine require considerable amount of time and efforts.

Thus a postprocess method to improve deformations and stresses through the thickness has been developed for symmetric cross-ply laminated plates[7] and shells[8]. The scheme of postprocess method is divided into two parts. The first is to set up the relationship between shear angles of FOPT and EHOPT. The second is to obtain deformation and stress fields from FOPT solution by using EHOPT displacement fields as a postprocessor. In symmetric cross-ply cases, the shear angle matching relationship of EHOPT and FOPT is quite simple. Just suppose the equivalence between transverse shear energy of FOPT and that of EHOPT. The finite element postprocess method was reported in refs[9,10]. However, the postprocess method is more complicated in the general lamination configurations[11].

The objective of the present study is to develop a postprocess method within finite element framework which works in general lamination layup configurations. The validity and efficiency of the finite element postprocess method are demonstrated for angle-ply layup. The accuracy of stress prediction is significantly improved compared to FOPT solutions. The numerical example will demonstrate the accuracy and efficiency of the present method.

II. Displacement Field of Postprocessor

1. FOPT(First Order Plate Theory)

The displacement field of FOPT is given as follows

$$u_a = u_a^o + y_a z, \quad u_3 = w(x_1, x_2) \quad (1)$$

where u_a^o and w are the in-plane stretching and out-of-plane deflection in the mid-plane, respectively. The rotational variable y_a is the angle at the mid-plane.

The transverse shear strain of FOPT can be expressed from the strain-displacement relationship.

$$g_{3a} = \frac{\partial u_a}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x_a} = y_a + w_{,a} = j_a \quad (2)$$

2. EHOPT(Efficient Higher Order Plate Theory)

The displacement field of EHOPT is obtained by superimposing linear zig-zag field on the smoothly cubic varying field through the thickness. The bottom surface is chosen as a reference plane.

$$u_a = u_a^o + y_a z + x_a z^2 + f_a z^3 + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} S_a^k \{(z - z_k) H(z - z_k)\}, \quad u_3 = w(x_1, x_2) \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of layers, and $H(z - z_k)$ is the Heaviside unit step function.

The number of unknowns are reduced by imposing top and bottom surface transverse shear free conditions ($S_{3a}|_{z=0,h} = 0$) and transverse shear stress continuity conditions at each interfaces between layers ($S_{3a}|_{z=z_k^+} = S_{3a}|_{z=z_k^-}$).

$$y_a = -w_{,a} \quad (4)$$

$$x_a = -\frac{3h}{2} f_a - \frac{1}{2h} \sum_{k=1}^N S_a^k \quad (5)$$

$$S_a^k = a_{ag}^k f_g \quad (6)$$

where a_{ag}^k can be determined by the layer transverse material properties and layer thickness. Detailed derivation of Eq.(6) can be found in Refs.[4,5]. By substituting Eqs.(4)-(6) into Eq.(3), the final form of the in-plane displacement field is reduced to following form

$$u_a = u_a^o - w_{,a} z + (z^3 - \frac{3h}{2} z^2) f_a + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} a_{ag}^k f_g \left\{ -\frac{z^2}{2h} + (z - z_k) H(z - z_k) \right\} \quad (7)$$

The transverse shear strains of EHOPT are obtained by the strain-displacement relationship.

$$g_{3a} = \frac{\partial u_a}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x_a} = 3(z^2 - hz) + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} a_{ag}^k f_g \left\{ -\frac{z}{h} + H(z - z_k) \right\} \quad (8)$$

III. Matching Shear Angle f_a

Both the transverse shear strain of FOPT and that of EHOPT are expressed in terms of the variables j_a and f_a , respectively. Thus from two plate theories, the shear angle f_a of EHOPT can be obtained in terms of the variable j_a of FOPT by assuming that the transverse shear energy of EHOPT is equal to that of FOPT.

However, when the transverse energy equivalence is imposed between first order theory and higher order theory, the matching relationship of rotational variables between FOPT and EHOPT cannot be constructed explicitly because of appearance of coupling term in the transverse shear energy. Thus in order to obtain the explicit matching relationship of rotational variables, a coordinate transformation with respect to the thickness coordinate z

should be carried out, which eliminates the coupling due to \bar{Q}_{45} in EHOPT. The direction of the principal axis is determined in terms of transverse shear modulus and ply thickness. The transverse shear strain energy in EHOPT is given as

$$U_c^{EHOPT} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13} \\ \mathbf{g}_{23} \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{55}^k & \bar{Q}_{45}^k \\ \bar{Q}_{45}^k & \bar{Q}_{44}^k \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13} \\ \mathbf{g}_{23} \end{Bmatrix} dz \quad (9)$$

where the shear strains are expressed as the linear combination of f_a .

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13} \\ \mathbf{g}_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{15z}^k & g_{14z}^k \\ g_{25z}^k & g_{24z}^k \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where g_{ijz}^k is a function of the thickness coordinate.

The transformed decoupled shear strain energies are expressed by using transformation of the shear angles.

$$\begin{aligned} U_c^{EHOPT} &= \int_0^h \{ \bar{Q}_{55}^* f_1'^2 + \bar{Q}_{45}^* f_1' f_2' + \bar{Q}_{44}^* f_2'^2 \} dz \\ &= A_{55}^* f_1'^2 + A_{45}^* f_1' f_2' + A_{44}^* f_2'^2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_1' \\ f_2' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos b & -\sin b \\ \sin b & \cos b \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (A_{44}^*, A_{45}^*, A_{55}^*) = \int_0^h (\bar{Q}_{44}^*, \bar{Q}_{45}^*, \bar{Q}_{55}^*) dz$$

The detailed expressions of \bar{Q}_{ij}^* are given in the ref[11] and they are omitted here for the limited space

The principal direction (b) can be determined by the condition $A_{45}^* = 0$.

$$b = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2A}{B} \right) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_0^h \{ \bar{Q}_{45} (g_{15z} g_{24z} + g_{14z} g_{25z}) + \bar{Q}_{44} g_{24z} g_{25z} + \bar{Q}_{55} g_{14z} g_{15z} \} dz \\ B &= \int_0^h \{ \bar{Q}_{55} (g_{14z}^2 - g_{15z}^2) + \bar{Q}_{44} (g_{24z}^2 - g_{25z}^2) + 2\bar{Q}_{45} (g_{14z} g_{24z} - g_{15z} g_{25z}) \} dz \end{aligned}$$

The transverse shear energy of FOPT is denoted as U_c^{FOPT} using constitutive relationships. The shear correction factors are introduced in FOPT to improve global response of FOPT. If we express the transverse shear energy using conventional shear correction factors k_1 and k_2 like refs[12-14], the shear angles of FOPT and EHOPT cannot be matched explicitly because the principal direction of EHOPT shear energy does not coincide with that of FOPT (See Fig.1). Thus we introduce additional off-diagonal shear correction factor k_3 , which can be determined in terms of k_1 and k_2 by the condition that U_c^{FOPT} has the same principal direction as U_c^{EHOPT}

$$U_c^{FOPT} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13}^f \\ \mathbf{g}_{23}^f \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \bar{Q}_{55}^k & k_3 \bar{Q}_{45}^k \\ k_3 \bar{Q}_{45}^k & k_2 \bar{Q}_{44}^k \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13}^f \\ \mathbf{g}_{23}^f \end{Bmatrix} dz \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13}^f \\ \mathbf{g}_{23}^f \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos b & -\sin b \\ \sin b & \cos b \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{13} \\ \mathbf{g}_{23} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Shear correction factor k_3 is expressed explicitly in terms of k_1, k_2 and principal direction b of EHOPT

$$k_3 = \frac{k_2 A_{44} - k_1 A_{55}}{2A_{45}} \tan 2b \quad (15)$$

where

$$(A_{44}, A_{45}, A_{55}) = \int_0^h (\bar{Q}_{44}^k, \bar{Q}_{45}^k, \bar{Q}_{55}^k) dz$$

In order to determine shear correction factors k_1 and k_2 of FOPT, an iterative *posteriori* process is adopted.

Transverse shear strain energy calculated from equilibrium equations is given as

$$U_e = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \begin{Bmatrix} S_{13}^k \\ S_{23}^k \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} g_{13}^f \\ g_{23}^f \end{Bmatrix} dz = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} \begin{Bmatrix} S_{13}^k \\ S_{23}^k \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{55}^k & \bar{S}_{45}^k \\ \bar{S}_{45}^k & \bar{S}_{44}^k \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} S_{13}^k \\ S_{23}^k \end{Bmatrix} dz \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} S_{13}^k \\ S_{23}^k \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos b & -\sin b \\ \sin b & \cos b \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} S_{13}^k \\ S_{23}^k \end{Bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$U_{13}^e = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (\bar{S}_{55}^* S_{13}^2 + \bar{S}_{45}^* S_{13} S_{23}) dz \quad (18)$$

$$U_{23}^e = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (\bar{S}_{44}^* S_{23}^2 + \bar{S}_{45}^* S_{13} S_{23}) dz$$

where \bar{S}_{ij}^* is the transformed compliance coefficient which are functions of \bar{S}_{ij} and principal direction b . The detailed expressions of \bar{S}_{ij}^* can be found in the ref[11].

The effective modulus A_{ij}^{eff} and shear correction factors $\bar{k}_1^{(i)}, \bar{k}_2^{(i)}$ are defined as follows

$$\bar{k}_1^{(i)} A_{55}^{\text{eff}(i)} = \frac{1}{2} \{ \bar{k}_1^{(i)} A_{55} (1 + \sec 2b) + \bar{k}_2^{(i)} A_{44} (1 - \sec 2b) \} \quad (19)$$

$$\bar{k}_2^{(i)} A_{44}^{\text{eff}(i)} = \frac{1}{2} \{ \bar{k}_1^{(i)} A_{55} (1 - \sec 2b) + \bar{k}_2^{(i)} A_{44} (1 + \sec 2b) \} \quad (20)$$

By equating shear strain energy obtained by equilibrium approach to the energy obtained by constitutive approach, the shear correction factors are determined through iteration procedure.

$$\bar{k}_1^{(i+1)} U_{13}^e = \frac{1}{2} \bar{k}_1^{(i)} A_{55}^{\text{eff}(i)} g_{13}^f{}^2 \quad (21)$$

$$\bar{k}_2^{(i+1)} U_{23}^e = \frac{1}{2} \bar{k}_2^{(i)} A_{44}^{\text{eff}(i)} g_{23}^f{}^2 \quad (22)$$

where the superscript i indicates the number of iterations.

After shear correction factors k_1, k_2, k_3 and principal direction b are determined, the shear angles of EHOPT can be expressed in terms of those of FOPT explicitly. They can be constructed by the equivalence of U_c^{FOPT} and U_c^{EHOPT} .

$$U_c^{\text{FOPT}} = U_c^{\text{EHOPT}} \quad (23)$$

Finally, the variable f_a^{EHOPT} are expressed in terms of j_a^{FOPT} with the linear factor C_{ab} .

$$f_a^{\text{EHOPT}} = C_{ab} j_b^{\text{FOPT}} \quad (24)$$

IV. In-plane Displacement Matching

In-plane stretching parts u_a^o of EHOPT should be corrected because the reference plane of EHOPT is different from that of FOPT. In-plane stretching parts u_a^o are obtained by eliminating EHOPT warping parts from FOPT in-plane displacement fields (See Fig.2). In the general lamination layups, the in-plane displacement field of EHOPT, u_1 can be expressed by separating it into two parts by the newly introduced u_{11} and u_{22} .

$$u_1 = u_{11}^o - w_{,1} z + (z^3 - \frac{3h}{2} z^2) f_1 + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} a_{11}^k \left\{ -\frac{z^2}{2h} + (z - z_k) H(z - z_k) \right\} f_1 + u_{12}^o + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} a_{12}^k \left\{ -\frac{z^2}{2h} + (z - z_k) H(z - z_k) \right\} f_2 \quad (25)$$

or in the compact form

$$u_1 = \frac{u_{11}^o - w_{,1} z + F_{11}(z) f_1}{u_{11}^{EHOPT}} + \frac{u_{12}^o + F_{12}(z) f_2}{u_{12}^{EHOPT}} \quad (26)$$

where $F_{11}(z)$ and $F_{12}(z)$ are the warping and coupling part of EHOPT, respectively. In the cross-ply layups, the coupling part $F_{12}(z)$ is zero because the coefficients a_{12}^k vanish.

The in-plane displacement fields of FOPT corresponding to those of EHOPT are given as

$$u_1 = y_1 z + u_1^o = u_{11}^{FOPT} + u_{12}^{FOPT} \quad (27)$$

The matching relationship of in-plane displacement between EHOPT and FOPT is constructed as follows

$$\int_0^h u_{ab}^{EHOPT} dz = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} u_{ab}^{FOPT} dz \quad (28)$$

From Eq.(28), the calculation of u_{11}^{EHOPT} is given as

$$u_{11}^{EHOPT} = \frac{1}{h} \left\{ \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} y_1^{FOPT} z dz + \int_0^h (w_{,1}^{EHOPT} z - F_{11}(z) f_1^{EHOPT}) dz \right\} \quad (29)$$

From this process u_{11}^{EHOPT} and u_{12}^{EHOPT} are determined.

In-plane stretching u_{22}^{EHOPT} and u_{21}^{EHOPT} can be determined in the same manner. However, when this process is continued, the transverse shear free conditions at top and bottom surfaces cannot be satisfied when we integrate the in-plane equilibrium equations through the thickness. To satisfy those boundary conditions, the in-plane equilibrium equations are imposed as constraints to modify the in-plane stretching variable u_{12}^{EHOPT} and u_{21}^{EHOPT} to satisfy transverse shear stress free conditions(See Fig.3).

To correct the variable u_{12}^o and u_{21}^o , we utilized the in-plane equilibrium equations. The in-plane equilibrium equations are given as follows

$$N_{1,1} + N_{12,2} = 0, \quad N_{12,1} + N_{2,2} = 0 \quad (30)$$

In-plane stretching parts u_{12}^o and u_{21}^o are modified as $C_1^o u_{12}^o$ and $C_2^o u_{21}^o$. The in-plane matching factors C_1^o and C_2^o are determined to satisfy Eq.(30) as constraints.

Now, the displacement fields of EHOPT are completely recovered in terms of the variables of FOPT in the general lamination configurations. The flowchart of the present postprocess method for general layups is given in Fig.4.

V. Finite Element Formulation

To formulate a finite element of first order plate theory, each primary variables are expressed in terms of shape function and nodal unknowns:

$$u_a^o = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i u_{ai}^o, \quad y_a = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i y_{ai}, \quad w = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i w_i \quad (31)$$

where n is the number of node points of an element and N_i is a shape function for the i th node. In the present study, the nine-noded iso-parametric elements are employed for the solution routine of FOPT.

The transverse shear stress of the postprocess phase is calculated accurately by integrating equilibrium equations through the thickness. Higher order derivatives of out-of-plane deflection w need to be calculated to obtain accurate transverse shear stresses. This makes

FEM implementation of the postprocess method difficult. Several procedures can be employed for the calculation of the higher order derivatives of deflections and they were described in the ref[10]. A finite difference method is used in the present study to obtain accurate third order derivatives of w .

VI. Numerical Examples and Results

Numerical solutions for anti-symmetric angleply are evaluated to assess the accuracy of the present postprocess method. The geometry and coordinates of laminate are shown in Fig. 5. The three dimensional elasticity solutions () of ref[15] for simply supported rectangular plates under sinusoidal loading are reproduced here for the comparisons. Two examples are considered.

Case 1 : [-30/30/-30/30] with uniform ply thickness.

Case 2 : [-45/45/-45/45] with uniform ply thickness.

Both plates are under sinusoidal loading conditions. In case 2, the principal direction (b) is -14.225 deg. The material properties for the 0-deg layer are

$$E_1 = 25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} , E_2 = 10^6 \text{ psi} , G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}$$

$$G_{23} = 0.2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} , n_{12} = n_{13} = n_{23} = 0.25$$

To facilitate the comparison with other theories, the following non-dimensional parameters are defined:

$$(\bar{S}_{xx}, \bar{S}_{yy}, \bar{S}_{xy}) = \frac{h^2}{q_o a^2} (S_{xx}, S_{yy}, S_{xy}) \quad (32)$$

$$(\bar{S}_{yz}, \bar{S}_{xz}) = \frac{h}{q_o a} (S_{yz}, S_{xz}) \quad (33)$$

$$(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) = \frac{E_2 h^2}{q_o a^3} (u, v) , \bar{w} = \frac{100 E_2 h^3}{q_o a^4} w \quad (34)$$

The 12 by 12 uniform meshes are used for the whole computations. The iterative scheme for the calculation of the shear correction factors are adopted and the results of the calculations of shear correction factors are given in Table 1. The computed shear correction factors of the present finite element approach agrees very well with those of the analytical method as shown in Table 1.

The results of the third order derivative calculations are given in Table 2. The present finite difference scheme provides quite accurate results compared to the results of the analytical approach. Even in the distorted mesh configurations, third derivatives can be obtained with reasonable accuracy. Thus the present method can provide reliable recovery of transverse shear stresses. The in-plane stresses of Case 1 are correlated well with those of elasticity solutions (Figs.7,8). The interlaminar shear stresses are also very accurately recovered by the present postprocessing technique as given in Fig.9. The recovered displacement of Case 2 shows some deviations from the 3-D elasticity solutions. Even though the coupling part of the displacement is not accurately recovered, the recovered warping displacement is compared well with that of 3-D elasticity (See Fig.11). Oncemore, the transverse shear stress are accurately predicted by using the equilibrium-equation-approach.

VII. Conclusion

The postprocess method for various layup configurations has been implemented within nine-noded iso-parametric finite element framework and numerical examples show its accuracy and efficiency. Not only matching of shear angles but also matching of in-plane displacement are required. In order to accurately predict global behavior of FOPT, iterative computational procedure is employed to obtain shear correction factors. To guarantee the transverse shear stress free boundary conditions, in-plane coupling part should satisfy

pointwise in-plane plate equilibrium. Thus matching relationship of general layup configuration is more complicated compared to symmetric cross-ply problems. However, the present postprocess method is still accurate and economical tool to provide the improved stress predictions compared to that of first order shear deformation theory.

Table 1 : Comparison of shear correction factor

	[-30/30/-30/30]		[-45/45/-45/45]	
	Analytical	FEM	Analytical	FEM
k_1	0.5661	0.5671	0.5286	0.5299
k_2	0.5595	0.5608	0.5286	0.5299
\bar{w}_{\max}	1.92166	1.918484	1.99269	1.98849

Table 2 : Comparison of third derivatives for [-30/30/-30/30] square laminated plate

$k_1 = k_2 = \frac{5}{6}$	Regular mesh	Distorted mesh	Analytical	Analytical
P	(1.8333, 0.1666)	(1.657, 0.1666)	(1.8333, 0.1666)	(1.657, 0.1666)
$w_{,yyy}$	1.665723	1.773276	1.70894	1.66153
$w_{,xxy}$	1.662453	1.638278	1.70894	1.66153
$w_{,xyx}$	1.650714	1.573495	1.70894	1.66153

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(a) Transverse shear strain energy in case of no coupling between j_1 and f_1

(b) Transverse shear strain energy in case of existence of coupling term

Figure 1 : Transverse shear strain Energy matching

Figure 2 : In-plane displacement matching

Figure 3 : Transverse shear stress boundary condition matching ($N_{ab,b} = 0$)

Figure 5 : Geometry and coordinate for typical laminate plate

Figure 6 : Iterative method for general layups

Figure 6 : Mesh configurations of third derivative's comparison

Figure 7 : In-plane stress $S_{xx}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2})$ through the thickness for case 1
 $w_{,xyx} = \frac{\Delta w_{,xy}}{\Delta x}$, $w_{,xxy} = \frac{\Delta}{\Delta y}$

Figure 10 : In-plane displacement $\bar{u}(\frac{a}{2}, 0)$ through the thickness for case 2

Figure 8 : In-plane stress $S_{xy}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2})$ through the thickness for case 1

Figure 11 : In-plane displacement $\bar{v}(\frac{a}{2}, 0)$ through the thickness for case 2

Figure 9 : Transverse shear stress $S_{yz}(\frac{a}{2}, 0)$ through the thickness for case 1

Figure 12 : Transverse shear stress $S_{xz}(\frac{a}{2}, 0)$ through the thickness for case 2